

Statistical Design of Experiment

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Design of Experiments (DoE) is an efficient exploration method that enables the systematic collection of data in a way that allows for statistical analysis. DoE enables the discovery and quantification of relationships between variables of interest (factors) and outputs (responses) [1]. This differs from one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) experimentation, which is a traditional intuition-led method that aims to hold all factors (X_i) constant while one is adjusted until a maximized response (Y_i) is obtained (Figure 1A) [2]. Consequently, this approach is incapable of identifying interactions between factors, whereby the configuration of one factor may impact the effect of another, potentially leading to the inaccurate identification of optimal settings. Conversely, the DoE approach allows the exploration of the entire design space with the simultaneous change of multiple factors with different values (level). These factors can be categorical, such as the type of carbon or nitrogen source in the medium, or quantitative indicating a numerical value such as temperature. The initial stage of identifying optimal values of the selected factors involves screening experiments to select the important treatment factors (Figure 1B). In practice, it may not be necessary to perform screening experiments, if there is sufficient prior knowledge of the investigated system [3]. After determining the most important factors, one can predict the response surfaces and find the optimal set points (Figure 1C) [1].

Factorial designs such as full-factorial, fractional factorial, and Plackett-Burman are commonly used for screening purposes [4]. Full factorial design requires performing experiments that include all possible factors and level combinations. The number of experiments can be calculated as below, where X represents the number of factors and L represents the number of levels.

$$\text{Number of experiments} = \prod_{i=1}^X L_i$$

The effect of the factor is defined as the main effect of that factor, calculated by taking into account the average of all the experiments, where the level of the factor is constant. Similarly, interactions between factors are achieved considering experiments where the levels of the studied factors change, regardless of the other factors. Moreover, in order to identify which factors and

interactions have a significant effect on the response variable, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) is employed. The model coefficients represent the degree to which factors, and their interactions affect the response [1,5].

Figure 1. Comparison of one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) and design of experiment (DoE) approaches. X_1 and X_2 represent experimental factors that can take continuous values, and the color gradient represents the value of true response (blue: low, red: high). This figure was adapted from the work of Bowden et al. (2019) [2]. **A)** OFAT follows a sequential testing strategy, and measurements are done at the indicated points. Once the optimal X_2 value is found then optimization of X_1 starts. With this approach, the identified optima is likely misleading. DoE allows changing multiple factors per experiment and provides eligible approaches for **B)** screening of factors and **C)** detailed response surface optimization.

Full-factorial design requires performing all combinations of factors and levels. Fractional factorial designs reduce the number of experiments required while allowing multiple factors to be screened to identify those with the greatest influence on response. These designs test two levels per factor and based on their resolution, can provide insights into both main effects and interactions. By preserving orthogonality among factors, they ensure that the effect of each factor is not confounded with changes in other factors and allow the estimation of some model parameters with fewer experiments [1]. In our work, we demonstrated a combinatorial approach to improve *C. oleaginosus* lipid production by performing a full factorial design that considers both genetic factors (*ACL*, *ACC*, *TS*) that positively impacted lipid content [6] and the low and high C/N ratios. The R code for full factorial design is available in the folder. Results were presented in the paper.

After obtaining the most important factors from the screening design, response surface methods (RSM) allow the researcher to describe in detail the relationship between the factors and the response and subsequently identify the optimal levels to maximize the investigated response. These methods such as central composite design, and Box-Behnken design use a quadratic model and require at least three levels of each factor to locate maximums or minimums in the response as a function of the factor settings. Subsequently, the generated model is used to identify optimal factor levels through the utilization of contour plots and canonical or ridge analysis [1]. Please refer to Dominici et al. (2014) for a detailed explanation of the design of experiment methods [1]. The DoE strategies have facilitated the optimization of bioprocess conditions [5,7–10], strain design [3,11–14], and simultaneous optimization of environmental and genetic factors [15,16].

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